

QUIZ**LAST NAME: RR****FIRST NAME: KRISHNAA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Prof. CLEENEWERCK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly software

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2010 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Do you think it is mandatory that all academic essays MUST contain references? Or what is the need for referencing in essay writing.**
 - Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offense.¹**
 - Referencing helps the reader to understand the source of the work.
 - Referencing aids in building supportive information for the essay.
 - Referencing authenticates the views of your essay.

2. **If two more clauses are grammatically complete and not joined by a conjunction, are to form a single compound sentence. As per “The Elements of Style” by Strunk, please choose the right sentence among the following options.**
 - Stevenson's romances are entertaining; they are full of exciting adventures.²**
 - Stevenson's romances are entertaining, they are full of exciting adventures.
 - Stevenson's romances are entertaining—they are full of exciting adventures.
 - Stevenson's romances are entertaining they are full of exciting adventures.

3. **Why a storyboard is suggested for a long project like a dissertation, but not an outline?**

¹EUCLID University, ACA-401 Coursepack, Period 1.

²Strunk, The Elements of Style, 2011 (17). Two grammatically completed sentences must be separated by semicolon.

- The problem is that an outline can force a student to specify too much too soon and so lock up a final form before the student has done his best thinking.³**
 - An outline cannot relatively be framed for a long project as a long project may contain many metrics of research.
 - Neither outline nor storyboard is suggested for long projects. A student can choose his option among outline or storyboard.
 - A storyboard will be more formal and creates better research interest than an outline in the minds of a researcher.
4. **Online resources used for research may be easy to obtained and stored in soft copy form. But do you think such sources can be reliable as no single or universal source authenticates its reliability. How do you ascertain the reliability of an online source before you apply it in your research work? Please choose one answer from the below which best suits the question.**
- The authenticity of online sources cannot possibly or practically be ascertained. Hence there is no need to check its reliability.
 - The site is sponsored by a reputable organization. It is related to a reliable professional journal. Site not being updated and non-mentioning of date are not relevant factors to be considered.
 - The site is sponsored by a reputable organization or is related to a reliable professional journal. It must indicate when the site was last updated. If it has no date, be cautious.⁴**
 - Choose only reliable sites that do not contain heated arguments or debating issues that are contentious.

³Kate L. Turabian, 2013. A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers (Chicago, University of Chicago Press), 22.

⁴Turabian, 29.

5. **What do you think is the greatest barrier that prevents students from progressing further in the doctoral studies though they show good inclination in the initial stages but fail in the last crucial moment in submitting a dissertation?**

- Students were simply unmotivated to move forward with the dissertation work. Having spent many years it might simply be that they lacked the necessary energy to continue.
- Significant psychological and social aspects that affect students' ability to carry out this work, most notably issues of self-efficacy and feelings of isolation. In many cases, psychological symptoms and social feelings of estrangement and/or isolation experienced by students may be a function of the ambiguity within which the academy portrays the research process during the coursework.⁵**
- In the absence of formal help either through coursework or faculty they had to rely on themselves and their colleagues to understand and carry out their research.
- The course materials do not adequately provide the requisite knowledge. There is a serious gap of knowledge between the course work and the research being performed by the students.

6. **Although many websites for government agencies, professional organizations, and educational institutions provide useful information, you should always evaluate information obtained from a website for:-**

- Currency, legitimacy, accuracy, and potential bias.⁶**
- Trifling, contentious and debatable issues.
- Free access and attractive materials.
- None of the above.

⁵ Bloomberg, Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, 143.

⁶ Bloomberg, Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, 52.

7. **You have done reviews of two dissertations of your choice. In your opinion what do you think among the following lays the foundation of review of good literature?**

- Doing good dissertation research
- Writing a good dissertation
- Using the literature well throughout the rest of one's career
- All of the above.**⁷

8. **What considerations a student expects in the right advisor?**

- Expertise, chemistry (good working rapport), good lines of communication, access and availability, listens to student's concerns and helps the student to deal with them. The advisor should have a genuine interest in helping the student succeed.**⁸
- Student and the advisor must be related to each other and have known each other before the doctoral program. The advisor must have a personal interest in the subject chosen by the student and pushes his personal views to be incorporated in the student's work.
- Student and the advisor have to be in the same field of work.
- None of the above.

9. **Among the following what specific advantage does Note-Taking offer to a student. Tick the right answer in reference to Turabian's "*A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations.*"**

- Note-Taking is a matter of merely recording data.

⁷ Gastel. Preparing the Literature Review Section of a Dissertation
<http://www.authoraid.info/uploads/resources/preparing-the-literature-review-section-of-a-dissertation.pdf>

⁸Bloomberg, Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, 17.

- Note-Taking advances the student's thinking.**⁹
- Note-Taking simply makes your report more readable.
- Note-Taking helps in finding additional solutions to the research problem.

10. **Which of the following statement is correct?**

- Parentheses and brackets must never be used interchangeably.
- Brackets, despite appearances, are not part of the subject. Parentheses, despite appearances, are part of the subject.
- Parentheses and brackets can be used interchangeably.
- Parentheses and brackets must never be used interchangeably.**¹⁰

⁹Turabian, 33.

¹⁰Strauss, The Blue Book of Grammar and Punctuation, 33-34.

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